

Study of Supply Chain Management of Fish

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Abstract:

Fish is one of the main food items in Kokan region. It Fulfill the expectations of test of fish lovers and provides various vitamins and nutrition, so all fish lovers always give first preference. To fish like Bangda, Surmai, Halwa, Paplet, Prawns Etc. Various types of fishes are available in local markets in Kokan region, but these fishes are not durables It Perishes in very short period, So the fish lovers from long distance cannot fulfill their desire If they want to satisfy their desire for fish food, they have to come in Kokan, alternatively they would have to rely on how the fish delivered to their nearest market. moreover the supply of fish must be reliable, of high quality and fresh for all these a supply chain that delivers fish to distant markets for form the coast becomes crucial.

Keywords: Fish Production, Supply Chain Management, PMMSY, Strategies.

Introduction:

More than 80% of people are non vegetarian in India. Most of the demand of food is satisfied with non vegetarian food which includes meat, chicken, eggs and fish, so the fish is most preferences food in India. People love to eat fishes coming from costal area and sea. But it is the most perishable item required to genuinely handle and delivered to consumer instantly for it's maintains of good quality It can be possible with the help of proper food supply chain.

Importance:

There are 70-75 % of the world's population eat non veg and only 20-25% population are known as vegetarian. In India non vegetarian population is around 70-80%, which consumes meat, chicken and fishes. According to NFHS-5 (2019-21) around 71.8% of women and 83.2% of men consume non veg in Maharashtra. If we see these numbers then we can say most of the people love eating non veg in their food.

Researcher analyzed the data from NFHS 2005-06 to 2019-21 for understanding the consumption trend is those 15 years for the study

conducted by world fish India in collaboration with Indian council of Agricultural Research and other Govt and international Bodies, That suggest the proportion of fish eaters increased from 66% to 72% between 2005-06 and 2019-21, Annual per capital fish consumption rose from 7.4 kg to 12.3 kg As well as India is a second largest producer of farmed fish in the world – fish imports rose five times between 2005 to 2020 from 14000 tones to 76000 tones.¹

Objectives:

The main objective of the study is to understand the supply chain of fish from Kokan region. To Study the challengers & issues in supply chain management of fish.

To study the PMMSY Government Scheme for fish supply chain modernization.

Study Area: Costal region of Maharashtra state from India.

Research Methodology: The research paper is in descriptive nature uses the secondary data from various reports available from fisheries dept. and news articles, website & books, research paper etc.

Fish Supply Chain:

Fish Supply chain is networks which linked the fishers to consumers, with intermediater like agents, wholesalers, processors, retailers etc. It involves traditional wet market and developing modern channels such as online shops, Supermarkets etc.

According to Palsam Karthik Kumar Goud, Mani Selvam J and Putluri Sai Kishore the fish marketing system in India Complex and multi-tired involving various stake holders, channels and processes that facilitate the movement of fish from the point to capture to the final consumer, According to their study markets are divided into three types such as primary Market, Secondary wholesale market and third one is Terminal Market.

Stages In Supply Chain:

- 1) Capture or Culture: The First stage of fish supply chain is the capturing or culturing means producing the fishes in or from marine creek or inland water bodies places and fish farmers produces the fishes in their fish form which would be supply to next parties of supply chain.
- 2) Landing Centers: After capturing the fishes small fisherman sent their collected fishes to the landing centers which were located at the nearest place of costal line.
- 3) Intermediater: Various agents, Vendors and wholesalers purchases the fishes from these sports where the fishermen sold their collected fishes. The fishes after that processed like cleaning, sorting and further processing.
- 4) Processing: Same fishes were purchased for value adding product by the processors That means transforms raw fish into ready to cook or eat product These Process includes marinating Pickling making Fish balls or pastes, adding ingredients or packaging to increase economic value.
- 5) Distribution: Fish supply chain includes most important part is distribution via various

transport facilities to various market places like supermarkets, sut markets, exporters etc.

- 6) Retail Consumption: - The last stage of fish Supply chain is the retail consumption Consumer is the last and important part of supply chain.

Channels:

In Maharashtra there are many channels for fish supply to consumer from the coastal region like Ratnagiri, Palghar. Fish supply flows with the help of various channels. They are categorized as Traditional or Direct Channel, Wholesale Focused Channel, Modern or Export Channels.

Traditional or Direct Channel: Is the Channel where fishermen direct sell fishes to consumer or auctioned fishes to vendors and then it goes to consumer.

In Wholesale focused channel there are wholesalers who purchases fishes from fishermen and then sell it to consumer with the help of vendor or retailers.

The Third type of channel is called as modern or export channel. In this chain fishermen sell their fishes to exporters or processor units, then these units process the raw fish into useable or ready to cook material like cleaning, making fish balls or pastes or pickles, processed it to increasing its life of use. Then this ready material or fishes sold in foreign market.

The last one type channel of fish supply Chain is known as modern channel for fish supply In which buyer can buys the fishes online from online sellers.

Challenges in Fish Supply Chain Management:

- 1) Fish is a perishable commodity which required cold storage. But in the supply chain it is challenge to store fish quality because of disruption from power outrages, inadequate refrigerated transport and lack of landing site cold storage. It leads to post harvest losses.
- 2) In adequate Landing Centers: There are inadequacy in landing centers and also lack of

hygiene so it causes contamination of very first stage of the supply chain.

- 3) Delay in transportation: Fish production always happens in remote coastal areas & there are long distance between production area and urban markets. So there is requires multi-model transportation which leads to delay and quality destruction.
- 4) Market Issues: Intermediaters always control the market so small scale fishers always earns little Prices always fluctuate due to seasonal changes, fuel vests and change in consumer preferences It create financial instability for every stakeholders in the chain.
High fuel prices and maintenance cost of cold storage equipment's causes high operational cost which affect the profit and small fishers and operators.
- 5) Environmental Issues: Due to change in climate and depilation, rising sea temperatures and ocean acidification, there are problems in fish production, which leads to unpredictable supply level of fish.
- 6) International Standards: Small scale Export Company has to comply with costly diverse international safety standards such as ISO Certificates, HACCP Etc. and also understand the trade laws & regulation.
- 7) Literacy and awareness: Lack of Literacy and awareness among the fisherman and the middlemen of supply chain causes various losses. They can not take advantages of various schemes from government so the purpose of improving supply chain of fish is not achieved.

Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana (PMMSY):

For Blue Revolution means sustainable development of fisheries sector, Govt of India. Invest 20050 Crore from 2020-2025 It Focuses or increasing fish production & reduction In post-harvest losses modernizing infrastructure supporting fisher mean and creating jobs through fish chain

with the help of financial aid, technology and capacity development.

PMMSY Stimulates Production and Productivity with utilizing reservoirs, new ponds wages and technologies. It enhance infrastructure for post-harvest facilities, value chains and traceability system. It modernizes the supply chain with improvement in market linkages product quality and safety, as well as creating digital identities (NEDP) for better service delivery. It also provide support to fishers, fish farmers, vendors SHGS, FFPDS, Entrepreneur, private firms and it helps Specially SC, ST, Women and differently abled individuals and promote employment through supply chain.

PMMSY provide fund to beneficiary in which share of center is 60% , states provide 40% for most activities. For North Eastern or Himalaya States higher Central share is 90%. Most of fund provides for grants Subsidies for Infrastructure, Technology, Insurance and working capital. It implemented by State Fisheries Department of India.

In Short PMMSY is very useful to India's fisheries sector for modernizing making there more productive and for prosperous and achieve the goal of blue revolution.

Procedure for application: apply for PMMSY Schemes proposal DPR (Detailed Project Report) SCP (Self Contained Proposals) to respective District Fisheries Office These Proposal or Report contains

1. Background of the implementing agency / individual & their credential & competencies including financial statement of previous 3 years in case of autonomous agencies, entrepreneurs.
2. Feasibility Reports.
3. Project Objectives.
4. Anticipated Benefits in quantitative terms e.g. Fish product employment
5. Cost benefits analysis.
6. Bio Security & Environment Concerning of land issue if any

7. Documentary evidence (Availability of land, license, permission etc.)
8. Sources of funding for implementation of project.
9. Clear timelines for completion of project.
10. Undertaking for no duplication of central funding for similar project by same agency.
11. Detailed cost estimate of project.
12. Presentation of detail of project before PAC NFOB.

Activities:

- 1) Development of Hatcheries
- 2) Construction of Crown Out & rearing ponds with input cost for culture activities.
- 3) Re- Circulatory Agriculture System (RAS)
- 4) Biofioc unit
- 5) Cages Culture in Reservoirs
- 6) Open Sea Cages
- 7) Sea Weed Culture
- 8) Bivalve Culture
- 9) Construction of Raceways for Front Farming
- 10) Ornamental & Recreational fisheries
- Support for Acquisition of deep-sea fishing fisheries
- 11) Upgradation of existing fishing vessals
- 12) Support for providing safety kits for fisherman
- 13) Providing boats & nets for traditional fisherman

These are the activities can supported by PMMSY. ⁱⁱ

PMMSY is able to achieve the goal as follows:

Fish production increased 13.75 Million Mt Tone. in fy 19 to 22 Million Mt Tone by fy 25 improving culture productivity from 3 tones per hectare to 5 tone per hectare, enhancing domestic fish consumption from 5 kg to 12 kg per capita, increasing contribution of the fisheries sector to

agriculture grass value added (GVA) from 7.28% in fy 19 to about 8% by fy 25, doubling export revenue from rs 46589 crore (US \$ 6.37 billion) in fy 19 to 1,00,000 crore (US \$ 13.68 billion) reducing post harvesting losses to about 10% , creating 55 lakh direct & indirect employment opportunities across the value chain. ⁱⁱⁱ

Conclusion:

The fish supply chain in Maharashtra is very important in providing food to fish lovers. Although there are more challenges like perishability of commodity, inadequacy in landing centers and storage facilities, transportation issues, market issues and environmental issues. This supply chain shows tremendous growth since 2019 to 2025 with the help of PMMSY the fish supply chain overcome somehow above issues for achieving the goal of PMMSY we need to aware about it all the people involved in the supply chain as well as potential fishers and other related people.

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